

The Investigation of Cloud Properties Using Coincident Wideband Dual-Altitude TOGA-COARE Observations

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INTRODUCTION

A study of TOGA-COARE data used to estimate microphysical cloud information is described. Coincident wideband passive microwave brightness temperature observations from radiometers on both the DC-8 aircraft (~ 11 km altitude) and the ER-2 aircraft (~ 20 km altitude) are used to investigate microphysical cloud profile conditions between the two aircraft. A wideband, nadir-viewed, dual-altitude comparison between TOGA-COARE brightness temperature (T_B) observations and computed brightness temperature values is the basis for the estimation procedure. A flexible radiative transfer model was used to compute wideband, nadir-viewed dual-altitude T_B values for a variety of microphysical cloud conditions. By varying the microphysical cloud parameters (e.g., particle size distributions and the hydrometeor density) and requiring that the comparisons remain consistent with the TOGA-COARE observations, the cloud conditions between the two aircraft can be estimated.

TOGA-COARE OBSERVATIONS

The Tropical Ocean Global Atmospheres, Coupled Ocean Atmosphere Response Experiment (TOGA-COARE) investigated the interaction between the atmosphere and the ocean in the warm pool region of the western Pacific from November 1992 through February 1993. The TOGA-COARE instruments of interest are the DC-8's Airborne Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (AMMR: 10.7, 18.7, 21, 37, and 90 GHz) and Airborne Microwave Moisture Sounder (AMMS: 90, 183.3 ± 2 , 183.3 ± 5 , and 183.3 ± 9 GHz) and the ER-2's Advanced Microwave Precipitation Radiometer (AMPR: 10.7, 19.35, 37, and 85 GHz) and Millimeter-wave Imaging Radiometer (MIR: 89, 150, 183.3 ± 1 , 183.3 ± 3 , 183.3 ± 7 , and 220 GHz). In addition, the downlooking DC-8 Airborne Rain Mapping Radar (ARMAR, 13.8 GHz) reflectivity provides general

cloud information for altitudes $\lesssim 9$ km and the ER-2 Cloud Lidar System (CLS) estimates cloud top altitudes.

This investigation focused on the TOGA-COARE observations from February 22, 1993 during the time period of 21:31:08 — 21:35:39 UTC (DC-8) and the coincident overflights of the ER-2 aircraft (21:33:14 — 21:38:08 UTC). These are flight segments over anvil and convective cloud regions. Of particular interest for this paper are the differences in the ER-2 and DC-8 183.3 GHz brightness temperature values during the time period of 21:31:08 — 21:31:43 UTC (DC-8) and 21:33:14 — 21:33:49 UTC (ER-2). Fig. 1 shows the high frequency (≥ 89 GHz) brightness temperature values for the ER-2 (Fig. 1a) and DC-8 (Fig. 1b). The three differences of interest are defined as (1) the ER-2 89 GHz channel subtracted from the DC-8 92 GHz, (2) the ER-2 183.3 ± 7 GHz channel subtracted from averaged DC-8 183.3 ± 5 and 183.3 ± 9 GHz channels and (3) averaged ER-2 183.3 ± 1 and 183.3 ± 3 GHz channels subtracted from the DC-8 183.3 ± 2 GHz channel. The differences for the 183.3 GHz channels are about -100 Kelvin, while for 90 GHz the differences are closer to ± 20 Kelvin. As suggested in Wang *et al.* [1], these differences are attributed to high altitude (≥ 10 km) frozen hydrometeors of sizes that effectively scatter radiation at frequencies ≥ 150 GHz. The cloud microphysical conditions between the two aircraft are estimated using a comparison with calculated T_B values.

COMPARISONS AND MICROPHYSICS

The calculated T_B values are generated using a planar-stratified scattering-based radiative transfer (RT) model [2]. This RT model requires as input vertical microphysical cloud profiles of temperature, relative humidity, height, and five hydrometeor parameters (per hydrometeor type): type (e.g., rain, cloud water, ice), density (g/m^3), particle average radius (a_0 , mm), particle intercept (N_0 , $\text{mm}^{-1}\text{m}^{-3}$), and a flag identifying if the particle has a monodisperse or

Figure 1: Brightness temperature values for frequencies ≥ 90 GHz: (a) DC-8 aircraft observations, (b) ER-2 aircraft observations.

polydisperse size distribution. If polydisperse, the drop size distribution is defined by:

$$N_D(D) = N_0 e^{\left(\frac{-D}{\lambda_{D0}}\right)}. \quad (1)$$

Initially these input profiles were obtained from the three dimensional Goddard Cumulus Ensemble (GCE) simulated microphysical cloud data [3]. The GCE microphysics is provided in vertical profiles of height, temperature, relative humidity, and the densities for cloud water, rain, cloud ice, snow and graupel. In addition, GCE drop size distributions are suggested in [3].

The particular GCE simulation used was numerically generated based on a composite aircraft and radiosonde sounding obtained on February 22, 1993 near the TOGA-COARE observations studied in this work. However due to the simulation process, slices through the 3-D GCE microphysics will not directly match the microphysics observed by the TOGA-COARE instruments. Thus the ARMAR radar profiles were used to generalize the TOGA-COARE microphysics below about 9 km (the maximum height of the radar reflectivities) and then comparable GCE pixel profiles were extracted from the GCE data set. The radar reflectivities over the DC-8 UTC time portion 21:31:08 — 21:31:43 show very little activity (≤ 10 dBZ) [1]. However, just beyond this time period, the radar reflectivities show an anvil structure tilting toward the UTC times of interest [1]. Due to the radar reflectivity structure and the T_B value differences, the microphysical profiles extracted from the GCE data set were selected

Figure 2: Computed brightness temperature values for frequencies ≥ 90 GHz: (a) 11 km altitude (for DC-8), (b) 20 km altitude (for ER-2).

to have the maximum amounts (~ 2 g/m³) of ice above 11 km. These selected GCE pixels are also identified by the GCE simulation as non-precipitating pixels. Eight such pixel profiles were obtained from the GCE data set and their wideband brightness temperatures computed using the RT model.

Using the drop size distributions suggested in [3] the brightness temperatures for 90 GHz and higher are shown in Fig. 2 (region A). In comparing these values with those shown in Fig. 1 at 21:33:14 — 21:33:49 UTC (ER-2), all calculated values for frequencies ≥ 150 GHz are too warm by up to 100 Kelvin with respect to the ER-2 observations at those frequencies. In comparing with the DC-8 observations, the calculated T_B values are too cool by 10-50 Kelvin for all frequencies shown. These comparisons indicate two items about the calculations: (1) there is not enough small-sized ice at the higher (≥ 11 km) altitudes and (2) there may be too much ice, or incorrectly-sized ice at the lower altitudes.

In attempting to correct for the inconsistencies described above, the frozen hydrometeor components of the GCE profile were replaced by averaged ice densities and drop size distributions as derived by Liu and Curry [4]¹. Liu and Curry obtained data from the Central Equatorial Pacific Experiment (CEPEX). CEPEX used a suite of aircraft for in-situ investigations of the microphysical

¹Note that the units of N_0 in Fig. 2 of [4] are incorrectly specified. The correct units are $m^{-3} \mu m^{-1}$.

characteristics and radiative properties of tropical cirrus in the TOGA-COARE region during March and April of 1993. Thus the storm microphysics of the CEPEX data should be similar to an average of the TOGA-COARE February 22, 1993 case.

The selected GCE profiles were modified such that all the cloud ice, snow, and graupel were replaced with the Liu and Curry (LC) densities and drop size distributions whenever $T \leq 273.15$ Kelvin, (i.e., at heights ≥ 5 km). The resultant T_B values are shown in Fig. 2 (region B). This region of Fig. 2 shows that while the computed high altitude 183.3 GHz channels match those of the ER-2 observations, all of the other frequencies and altitudes do not match those of the TOGA-COARE observations in the 21:33:14 — 21:33:49 UTC (ER-2) time frame. The low altitude, high frequency calculations are too cold with respect to the DC-8 observations by 5–90 Kelvin. The high altitude, high frequency calculations are too cold (by 10–60 Kelvin) for 90 and 150 GHz. These unfavorable comparisons indicate that the LC densities and drop size distributions will require further adjustment prior to obtaining a favorable comparison.

After evaluating many ice density and drop size distributions, the best microphysical parameterization used the LC densities (M_{LC}) when $T \leq 273.15$ Kelvin. However below 11 km the Sekhon-Srivastava (SS) [5] ice drop size distribution was used. For the SS particles:

$$a_0 = 0.422M_{LC}^{0.524} \quad (2)$$

$$N_0 = 2545.52M_{LC}^{-1.093} \quad (3)$$

were used in (1). Above 11 km the LC densities and drop size distributions were used. Since Liu and Curry averaged the in-situ CEPEX observations to obtain their densities and drop size distributions, additional ice was required to simulate the extreme ice conditions of the TOGA-COARE 21:33:14 — 21:33:49 UTC (ER-2) time frame. This was accomplished by nearly doubling M_{LC} in the layers above 11 km. For the second ice contribution, M_{LC} was used in (2) and a_0 further divided by 3; the N_0 from (3) was retained. Thus the LC densities were almost doubled, an exact doubling would have occurred if N_0 was adjusted along with $a_0/3$. Since the SS drop size distribution has a larger radius than the LC drop size distribution they tend to increase the scattering and over cool the high frequency calculations. In fact, not dividing the radius by 3 reduced the high frequency, high altitude T_B values to 5–10 Kelvin below that observed.

The resultant brightness temperatures for the modified drop size distributions are shown in Fig. 2 (region C). In comparing these with the observations on February 22, 1993 from 21:33:14 — 21:33:49 UTC (ER-2), the results are favorable. All high frequency T_B values are within

± 10 Kelvin of the observations. For the low frequencies, all calculations are within ± 10 Kelvin of the observations, except for the 37 GHz channel calculations that are up to 15 Kelvin too warm.

CONCLUSIONS

This investigation used a wideband, nadir-viewed, dual-altitude comparison between TOGA-COARE DC-8 and ER-2 observed T_B imagery to estimate microphysical cloud conditions between the two aircraft. Initially the microphysical cloud properties used in the RT model were derived from the Goddard Cumulus Ensemble [3]; a simulated three-dimensional cloud initialized with TOGA-COARE observations. This investigation showed that for the observations on February 22, 1993 for the ER-2 time of 21:33:14—21:33:49 UTC, significant amounts of small-sized ice particles must be included above 11 km to obtain consistency with the TOGA-COARE observations. A more detailed investigation is underway to (1) study other TOGA-COARE DC-8, ER-2 coincident data sets, and (2) to convert ARMAR data into microphysical parameter profiles and to use those profiles along with the CLS cloud top heights in the radiative transfer calculations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J.R. Wang, J. Zhan, and P. Racette, "Multiple Aircraft Microwave Observations of Storms Over the Western Pacific Ocean," *Radio Sci.*, in press.
- [2] G.M. Skofronick-Jackson and A.J. Gasiewski, "Nonlinear statistical retrievals of ice content and rain rate from passive microwave observations of a simulated convective storm," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing*, Vol. 33, pp. 957-970, July, 1995.
- [3] W.-K. Tao and J. Simpson, "Goddard cumulus ensemble model. Part I: Model description," *Terres., Atmos., and Oceanic Sci.*, Vol. 4, pp. 35-72, March 1993.
- [4] G. Liu and J. A. Curry, "Remote sensing of ice water characteristics in tropical clouds using aircraft microwave measurements," *J. Appl. Met.*, in press.
- [5] R.S. Sekhon and R.C. Srivastava, "Snow size spectra and radar reflectivity," *J. Atm. Sci.*, pp. 299-307, 1970.